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Event Marketing Strategies And Customers Patronage Of Luxury Hotels In Yenagoa And Port Harcourt

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the impact of Event Marketing Strategies and Customers patronage of Luxury Hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt, the study implores a survey research design and use Spearman rank correlation to investigate the relationship between event sponsorship, customers preference , repeat patronage, referral. The significance of the study on "Event Marketing Strategies and Customers patronage of Luxury Hotels in Yenagoa and Port harcourtr" extends to various stakeholders, including the government, policy makers, business owners, investors, employees, researchers, and academicians. The findings reveal strong evidence of significant positive relationships between the event sponsorship, customers preference , repeat patronage, and referral of luxury hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt

Keywords: Event Marketing, Customer Patronage, Luxury, Strategies.

INTRODUCTION

The crucial aspect of every business is customers and their patronage, which enables business concerns to establish transactions that generate return on investment, whereby recouping capitals invested in the business and making profit. These profits enable the business to survive and grow amidst the dynamic competitive business environment. Hence the life line of every business is the pay they get from their customers. Timelio (2021) argues that cash could be seen as the only life and death issue every business has and that even the employees of businesses can't wait for their salary until the customers pay. For this reason, every business including the luxury hotels strive to generate customer patronage so as to acquire these inflows of cash for survival and running of their business.

But of lately, due to the corona virus pandemic and its resultant economic hardship, several hotel establishment in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt have experience poor customer patronage. That is why Bello and Bello (2021) in their study found out that the consequences of corona virus pandemic on Nigeria hospitality industry include sharp drop in hotel occupancy rates and low customers' patronage in other hospitality facilities, and mass sales of hospitality business facilities. Before the pandemic, there has been tremendous growth in luxury hotel businesses in Nigeria. A large number of luxury hotels are found in the major cities in Nigeria. Despite the large number of luxury hotels in the major cities in the country, more hotel businesses were being established. These growths of luxury hotels have increased the level of competition in the hotel industry. This increased competition has resulted in fierce competition amongst the luxury hotels coupled with the corona pandemic hardship; hence they are battling to survive as they intensify efforts to increase their level of customer patronage at this period. Increasing customer patronage seems to be the only way for these organizations to survive as Choi and Chu (2001) stated that increased customer patronage is the only way for hotels to maximize profit and survive in the competitive settings of the industry. Therefore, every luxury hotel firms is intensifying its efforts to increase their

level of customer patronage. However, in order for luxury hotels to increase their level of customer patronage, they need to adopt certain marketing practice such as event marketing as a key strategy to lure customer patronage.

Customers at this period of time needs activities that will keep their minds of the negative vibes the pandemic, insurgency and economic challenges have brought, and any business that will offer them good customer experience which will make them happy and forget the stress and hardship faced at the moment will definitely win their patronage. Entertainment events such as Big Brother Naija, Gulder Ultimate Search, Night of a Thousand Laughs are among popular events in Nigeria that have caught high viewership, and organizations have utilized these opportunities to sponsor these events and showcase their brands and offerings to the large audience of the shows. According to Nda-Isaiah (2021), **Big Brother Nigeria no doubt is the most-watched and biggest show in the country which season 6 that ended October 3rd 2021** according to the organizers recorded one billion votes this year from the viewers. The headline sponsor of the show was Abeg and the associate sponsor was Patricia, while other sponsors included Travelbeta, Darling hair, WAW, Innoson Motors, and RevolutionPlus Property (Olonilua, 2021).

Statement of the Problem

The major challenge facing luxury hotel operators in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt is how to increase the level of customer patronage in the midst of intense competition and economic downturn caused by corona virus pandemic and insecurity in the Country. Many hotels in mostly Port Harcourt and Yenagoa in South-South Nigeria are finding it difficult to increase their level of customer patronage in the face of intense competition. Some luxury hotels have ceased from operations due to poor level of customer patronage while some of the luxury hotels that are still in business are struggling to increase customer patronage.

The proliferation of new hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt have constituted a threat to existing luxury hotels as they feel that they might lose some of their customers to the new competitors. Consequently, this study suggests event marketing strategies and its dimensions of events sponsorship, use of corporate entertainment, and event communication as a way out of this challenge.

Several studies have tried investigating event marketing and business performance (Liu et al., 2016; Wu, 2016; Alan et al., 2017; Altschwager et al., 2017; Rachmadhian & Chaerudin, 2019; Sun et al., 2021; Kwon & Cornwell, 2021), but there tend to exist scarce empirical research work within the context of Yenagoa and Port Harcourt which considers event marketing strategies as it relates to customers patronage in luxury hotels being moderated by perceived corporate image and have three dimensions of event sponsorship, corporate entertainment and event communication as against the three measures of customers' preference, repeat patronage and referral, hence our point of departure. This creates a gap which this study tends to empirically fill.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study is to find out the relationship between event marketing strategies and customers patronage of luxury hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt.

While the specific objectives included to:

1. evaluate the extent of relationship between event sponsorship and customers preference of luxury hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt
2. evaluate the extent of relationship between event sponsorship and repeat patronage of luxury hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt
3. evaluate the extent of relationship between event sponsorship and referral of luxury hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt

Research Questions

Based on the objectives of the study, the following research questions were formulated:

1. To what extent does event sponsorship relates to customers preference of luxury hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt?
2. To what extent does event sponsorship relates to repeat patronage of luxury hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt?

3. To what extent does event sponsorship relates to referral of luxury hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were given for the study:

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between event sponsorship and customer preference of luxury hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt.

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between event sponsorship and repeat patronage of luxury hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt.

Ho₃: There is no significant relationship between event sponsorship and referral of luxury hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt.

METHODOLOGY

This chapter focused on the methods and techniques employed in conducting this research work, bearing in mind that every research work is geared towards adding to an existing knowledge or creating a new one. Basically, there are some assumptions in marketing research which enables researchers determine the methodology and design to be applied in their study. Again, social scientists have an objective and subjective views of their subject matter (Burrell & Morgan, 2006), and these are; ontological, epistemological, and human nature. In this study we ontologically took a realist view point, a positivist epistemology and a deterministic human nature.

In this study, we adopted mix method research design which combines both qualitative (use of interview) and quantitative (use of copies of questionnaire) research design. We adopted the mixed research design method so that we can have the views of customers and as well that of the management staff of luxury hotels together which enabled us make more informed decisions and give better recommendation to the hotel management. Creswell and Creswell (2018) argues that there are three approaches to research design which includes qualitative, quantitative and mixed method research design. This study was conducted in a non-contrived setting, in which the researcher has no complete control of the research elements.

The population for our study consisted of the customers and management of registered luxury hotels in Port Harcourt and Yenagua in South-South Nigeria and all those who visit the hotel which includes the working crowd, leisure customers, students, couples and others who visit for dining, relaxation, working and other purposes in Port Harcourt and Yanagua, in Rivers and Bayelsa states. This population is an infinite population and the management staff and customers considered in the study as our infinite population were that of 61 registered and functional luxury Hotels in Port Harcourt and Yenagua both in South-South Nigeria which were enlisted in businesslist.com and Finelib directory.

Since the study population was noted to be an infinite population, we deployed the Godden (2004) sample size formula, to determine the appropriate sample size for the study.

Formula

$$SS = \frac{Z^2 \times (p) \times (1 - p)}{C^2}$$

Where:

SS = Sample Size for infinite population

Z = Z - value (e.g., 1.96 for a 95 percent confidence level)

P = Population proportion, expressed as decimal (assumed to be 0.5 (50%) since this would provide the maximum sample size)

C = Confidence interval, expressed as decimal (e.g., 5% expressed as = 0.05)

Hence:

Z = 1.96

P = 0.5

C = 0.05

Therefore, $SS = \frac{1.96^2 \times (0.5) \times (1 - 0.5)}{0.05^2}$

$SS = \frac{3.8416 \times 0.25}{0.0025}$

$SS = \frac{0.9604}{0.0025} = 384.16$ Approx. = **384** as sample size

Hence our sample size from the infinite population using Godden (2004) method is three hundred and eighty four (384).

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

In order to select the sample of 384 from the 61 functioning luxury hotels in Port Harcourt and Yenagoa in Rivers and Bayelsa state, the researcher used convenient sampling technique which is a non-probability sampling technique to conveniently select a minimum of six (6) customers from each of the 61 identified luxury hotels and a copy of questionnaire were given to each of them, and also the study interviewed 10 staff, which were made up of two (2) selected management staff from each of the five most popular luxury hotels in Port Harcourt and Yenagwa in South-South Nigeria namely Presidential Hotel, Landmark Hotels, Protea Hotel Port-Harcourt, Novotel Port Harcourt, Ayalla Hotels Limited Yenagwa so as to generate opinions from both customers and management staff of the luxury hotels.

Validity relates to the ability of an instrument to measure what it is supposed to measure (Nwankwo, 2010; as cited in Nwaogazie, 2014). While Knehta et al. (2019) suggested that validity checks whether a particular instrument in realty measures what it is designed to measure.

Most of the scales used in this study were generated by modifying existing scales which were already reported to be reliable and valid in past research studies. Modifications were made in the wording of some of the statement items to sooth the specific context used in this study. The questionnaire for this study was validated by three experts in the department of marketing in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education for face and content validity.

Data Analysis and Results

In this section, it was shown how the data distributed and retrieved from the data base (respondents) where analyzed. It began with the demographics analysis of the respondents, then progressed to univariate analysis of the statement items of the research questionnaire, and to the bivariate analysis of the dimensions and measured of study using Pearson correlation coefficient and regression analysis. It also treated the multivariate analysis of the moderating variable on the relationship between the predictor and the criterion variable using partial correlation.

Demographic Analysis

Table 4.2: Frequencies on Gender of Respondents

Gender		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Female	130	35.8	35.8	35.8
	Male	233	64.2	64.2	100.0
Total		363	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Figure 4.1 – Bar Chart showing frequencies for Gender

From the analysis in table 4.2 above, we can see that 130 (or 35.8%) of the respondents are female while 233 (or 64.2%) of them are male.

Figure 4.2 – Pie Chart showing frequencies for Gender

Table 4.3: Frequencies on Age Bracket of Respondents

		Age Bracket			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	20-25yrs	92	25.3	25.3	25.3
	26-30yrs	189	52.1	52.1	77.4
	31 & Above	82	22.6	22.6	100.0
	Total	363	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2021.

Figure 4.3 – Bar Chart showing frequencies for Age Bracket

Figure 4.4 – Pie Chart showing frequencies for Age Bracket

Figure 4.5 – Histogram showing normality curve for Age Bracket

Reports from table 4.3 on the analysis of age bracket of the respondents reveals that 92 (or 25.3%) are within the range of 20-25 years, 189 (or 52.1%) are within the age range of 26-30 years; 82 (or 22.6%) are within 31 & above. The histogram in fig 4.5 shows that the population is normally distributed.

Table 4.4: Frequencies on Respondents' Level of Education

Valid	Level of Education	Level of Education		Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
		Frequency	Percent		
	High School	13	3.6	3.6	3.6
	Under Graduate	212	58.4	58.4	62.0
	Graduate	138	38.0	38.0	100.0
	Total	363	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2021.

Figure 4.6 – Bar Chart showing frequencies for Level of Education

Figure 4.7 – Pie Chart showing frequencies for Level of Education

Figure 4.8 – Histogram showing normality curve for Level of Education

From Table 4.4, it shows that 13 (or 3.6%) of the respondents are high school graduates; 212 (or 58.4%) of the respondents are under graduates; 138 (or 38.0%) are graduates. Also the histogram in fig 4.8 shows that the population is normally distributed.

Table 4.5: Frequencies on Respondents’ Length of Patronage

		Length of Patronage		Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
		Frequency	Percent		
Valid	1 - 5 months	80	22.0	22.0	22.0
	6months - 1 year	200	55.1	55.1	77.1
	2 years & Above	83	22.9	22.9	100.0
Total		363	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Figure 4.9 – Bar Chart showing frequencies for Length of Patronage

Figure 4.10 – Pie Chart showing frequencies for Length of Patronage

Figure 4.11 – Histogram showing normality curve for Length of Patronage

The analysis in table 4.5 above reveals how long each respondent has been patronizing the luxury hotel. 80 (or 22.0%) of the respondents have patronized the hotel for 1-5 months, 200 (or 55.1%) of them have patronized the business for 6 months-1 year, while 83 (or 22.9%) have patronized the business for 2 years and above.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the discussions of findings, the study concluded that there is a significant positive relationship between event marketing strategies and customers' patronage of luxury hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt.

That is there a significant positive relationship between event sponsorship, corporate entertainment, event communication, and the measures of customers' patronage of luxury hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt.

Also, that perceived corporate image significantly influences the relationship between event marketing strategies and customers' patronage of luxury hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Since the result of the study shows a positive significant relationship between event marketing strategies and customers' patronage, luxury hotel management should adopt the use of

event sponsorship strategy in order to improve chances of brand awareness and achieve image transfer from big well known events to the brand.

2. Also, luxury hotel management needs to adopt the use of corporate entertainment such as the use of comedians and music concerts to amuse and entertain its audience since it has proven to help encourage customers' patronage.

3. Lastly, they should adopt the use of event communication strategies such as the use of social media platforms in order to have maximum reach to audience in regards to the event whereby creating awareness.

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